
**THE FRANCISCAN RECONSTRUCTION OF THE CHURCH OF S. FERMO IN
VERONA IN THE ARCHITECTURAL CONTEXT OF THE VENETIAN
GOTHIC (13TH-14TH CENTURIES)**

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Abstract

The article deals with the reconstruction of the church of Saint Fermo Maggiore in Verona, implemented by the Franciscans between the 13th and 14th centuries. Thanks to the precise research of Gianpaolo Trevisan and the 3D digital surveys carried out between 2016 and 2018, it was possible to establish the architectural diachrony of the church starting from the Romanesque foundation of the Benedictines in 1065. The Franciscans replaced the Benedictines in 1261 and transformed the church: they extended and raised the entire construction making it a single-hall one, dominated by the immense wooden ceiling with an upturned ship's bottom. On the other side, the Friars Minor maintained the wide Romanesque crypt, which follows the whole length of the church. The church of Saint Fermo became a structural counterpoint to the mother basilica of Saint Francesco in Assisi, qualifying as an unusual protagonist in the Venetian Gothic architectural context.

Keywords: Church of Saint Fermo Maggiore in Verona, Gothic Architecture, Franciscans.

1. The Benedictine architectural site (11th century)

The monastery of Saint Fermo Maggiore in Verona stands on a Roman cemetery area, outside the ancient Porta dei Leoni (called *Porta Sancti Firmi* in the Middle Ages). The early Christian basilica (5th-6th century) had a long rectangular plan: in this cemetery basilica, as narrated by the *translatio* of saints Fermo and Rustico, the bishop Annone (750-772) placed the remains of the two martyrs and built a semicircular sanctuary (*confessio*) with an altar for the relics (*arca saxea*) (Hudson, 2004).

The early Christian building was used until the 11th century when the Benedictines took over from the secular clergy. The monks rebuilt the church from the ground up: an inscription on a pillar of the crypt recalls that the building site began in 1065. The Romanesque church no longer exists, but the current building still respects its perimeter. The construction consisted of three main structures: the underground crypt, the church and an *avant-corps* (Trevisan, 2008).

The crypt has a floor plan with four naves and five apses in stepped lay-out (Fig. 1). This particular Cluniac planimetry (*chevet échelonnée*) derives from Burgundy, but was also widely used both in a series of churches in the 11th century in the north-western Po valley area (Fruttuaria abbey, Acqui cathedral, Bobbio cathedral, Saint Giusto a Susa) (Trevisan, 2013, pp. 60-65) and in Tuscany, in the ancient cathedral of Saint Reparata in Florence. The crypt of Saint Fermo is so large that it is erroneously defined as the 'lower church', qualifying it as an autonomous architectural space. From an architectural and liturgical point of view, however, it is a crypt not separated from the church which had the function of monumental repository for the relics of saints Fermo and Rustico (in northern Italy, the only crypt of such large dimensions is that of Saint Sepolcro in Milan, founded in 1030). All the architectural and decorative elements of the crypt refer to Roman antiquity: tapered pillars, molded frames and reused capitals. The walls alternate bricks and stone with a great color effect: this particular two-tone, used for the first time in Saint Fermo, became the main feature of Veronese Romanesque architecture in the 12th century (Fig. 2).

The Romanesque church was a basilica with three naves divided by pillars (major and minor) and was preceded by a forepart which had privileged burials near the relics of the two martyrs. Along the walls there were pentagonal buttresses (one of the most widespread elements of Veronese Romanesque architecture), which suggest the original existence of transverse arches to support the wooden roof (Trevisan, 2004a, pp. 247-250).

The eastern elevation was restored between 1905 and 1914: at that time the two southern apses were completely rebuilt by replicating the two northern apses. Therefore, only the lower portion of the main apse and the two northern hemicycles belong to the Romanesque church, with double arched arches and classical Corinthian capitals with Venetian influences deriving from the construction site of Saint Marco in 1063 (Trevisan, 2016, pp. 98-99).

The elaboration of constructive ideas coming from different directions was the hallmark of the builders active in the building site of Saint Fermo: the city of Verona, indeed, was at the crossroads of the main ways for cultural exchanges among the Po valley, the lagoon area and the northern-Europe, with which Verona has always had a special relationship. The maximum expression of European references, however, was achieved in the architectural complex of Saint Lorenzo (beginning of the 12th century), a direct emanation of the basilica of Saint Fermo, which marked the transition from Proto-Romanesque to mature Romanesque architecture (Passuello, 2018, pp. 191-202).

2. The Franciscan architectural site (13th-14th centuries)

In 1261 the Franciscans officially acquired the monastery of Saint Fermo and started an impressive construction site that lasted until the mid-14th century. Thanks to the researches carried out by Gianpaolo Trevisan (2004b, pp. 175-182) and the graphics produced by the 3D laser-scanner digital survey made between 2016 and 2018 during the conservative restoration of the wooden ceiling (orthophotoplans of sections and elevations in scale 1:50, published in this article for the first time), it is possible to precisely define the architectural interventions implemented by the friars.

The first phase (1261-end of the 13th century) concerned the eastern sector of the church: the walls of the *chevet* were raised and the imposing triumphal arch was built. The triumphal arch served as a link between the central nave, which was raised and lengthened at a later time, and the main apse, which was subsequently rebuilt. Furthermore, the round arches giving access to the side chapels were opened (Fig. 3). The works continued with the construction of the large lateral arches of the transept, using a masonry that alternates stone and brick on the sides facing the interior of the hall. While the three internal naves were being dismantled, the construction site continued from east to west, raising the side walls to the height of the transept arches.

In this period, the religious functions were celebrated in the crypt, which always maintained its liturgical function and was never altered in its original structure. To access the hypogeum, the friars opened a large portal with an ogival arch in the southern side of the church (late 13th century): that passage directly connected the crypt to the cloister, which certainly existed in 1275 and of which, today, what remains is only the eastern side with a large pointed arch portal in stone and bricks and round double-arched windows with paired columns and rounded capitals.

The second phase (1314-1327/32) had as protagonists Guglielmo da Castelbarco, who financed the ambitious project to complete the church, and the friar Daniele Gusmari. Their portraits in the triumphal arch are the most visible testimony of their role in the architectural construction site, which has 1314 as its starting year, mentioned in an inscription next to Gusmari's portrait.

The new work plan represented a variant of the previous construction site. The new central polygonal apse was built, with large quadrangular buttresses surmounted by triangular pinnacles and spiers.

The most important innovations, however, were made in the roof system of the church: the immense wooden ceiling with an upturned ship's bottom was built in the central nave. This ceiling is truly exceptional for its incredible structure formed of sixteen trusses in red larch 54 m long (Frustoli, Soardo, 2009) (Fig. 4). Cross vaults were built in the presbytery and in the transept, with the consequent elevation of the surrounding walls. Even the sides were raised with a brick masonry and were enriched with variegated decorations: stone friezes with trefoil arches and diamond-shaped frames, brick friezes with circles and crosses.

The church was lengthened by about 24 m starting from the Romanesque façade, incorporating the ancient avant-corps and reaching the current volumetric and longitudinal development (Fig. 5). A walkable partition wall, about 4 meters high, was built to divide the space reserved for the religious from that reserved for the worshippers: this structure crossed the nave transversely and was in direct communication with the convent, to the south (De Marchi, 2007, pp. 138 -141). The construction of the new façade, completed by 1327, was the end of the second phase of the works, even if some finishes (cusps, crowning elements, sculptures) were carried out in the third decade of the 14th century, until Gusmari's death in 1332. The façade exceeded the western elevation of the ancient avant-corps by about 8 m (Trevisan, 2007, pp. 143-146) and has a profile with two salient

features. The front is divided into three horizontal parts: in the lower part there is the large splayed round arched portal, flanked by polylobed blind arches and single lancet windows with pointed arches and double columns. In the intermediate part, characterized by a two-tone masonry that alternates stones and bricks, there are four large trefoil windows that illuminate the interior of the church. Finally, in the upper part, there is a trifora flanked by two circular windows and a series of hanging arches under the slopes of the roof (Fig. 6). The façade, while using typically Gothic decorative forms, in its structural polychromy is still linked to the Romanesque building tradition, which was never abandoned even in the Gothic era.

3. The architectural context

When the Franciscans took over from the Benedictines in the custody of the venerated remains of the martyrs Fermo and Rustico, they had a building that recalled in an exemplary way the two superimposed churches of Saint Francesco in Assisi, which keep the remains of the founder of the Order (Bourdua, 2004, pp 32-70). For this reason, the friars did not modify the large Romanesque crypt, which was the memorial of the relics of saints Fermo and Rustico, but concentrated only on the reconstruction of the church according to the new Gothic architectural canons: an immense hall with a protruding transept and an eastern with three large arched chapels (Fig. 7).

This architectural scheme spread from the second half of the 13th century in the Veneto region with multiple variations. As in other Italian regions, the Gothic architectural style took hold in Veneto thanks to the architectural feats of the mendicant orders: for the Franciscans and Dominicans, however, Veneto played a role of considerable significance. In Padua, indeed, the minor friars founded the great basilica dedicated to saint Antonio, a favorite pupil of saint Francesco, who died in Padua in 1231. The basilica of Saint Antonio is one of the major sanctuaries of Christianity: with its complex structure, it demonstrates the transition from the Romanesque to the Gothic style, incorporating heterogeneous forms and influences over a very long time starting from 1235. The church, with a cruciform plan, was the first vaulted building in the Venetian mainland after the 11th century. In 1263 the tomb of saint Antonio was transferred to the presbytery, but the construction site continued with the erection of a second transept, the ambulatory and the new choir, where the tomb was placed in 1307. The choir, inspired by the Gothic creations of Ile-de-France,

was damaged in 1394 and rebuilt by 1424, and included an ambulatory with a triforium, a series of radial chapels and two towers.

Before the emergence of churches with vaults, in Veneto the single hall with three apsidal chapels had an extraordinary fortune: this architectural form, in its constructive essentiality, responded to the ideals and liturgical needs of the friars. The oldest structure of this type is Saint Giustina in Monselice (Padua), which dates back to the second quarter of the 13th century.

From the second half of the 13th century similar churches were built in most of the Venetian cities. The constructions were implemented with the addition of chapels with polygonal termination in the presbytery: examples are Saint Francesco in Treviso (1260), which is the closest comparison with Saint Fermo, and the Eremitani in Padua (1276). In these churches the height between the main chapel of the choir and the side chapels is almost equal, so as to obtain uniform lighting in the eastern sector.

The enormous appeal of the Dominicans and the Franciscans in the Venetian cities, indeed, imposed the creation of ever larger ecclesial spaces which, with the erection of cross vaults, welcomed more the models of the French Gothic. In Vicenza, the Dominicans built the church of Saint Corona (starting from 1260) with vaults and flat-topped presbytery chapels; in the same city the Franciscans began the construction of Saint Lorenzo (starting from 1281), a cross-shaped basilica with cross vaults and a three-room choir with polygonal apses, which follows Cistercian plans. The prototype of Saint Lorenzo had a large following especially among the Dominicans, who supplanted the Franciscans in the role of promoters of Gothic architecture with vaults in the Veneto region: examples are Saint Agostino in Padua (1290), Saint Anastasia in Verona (1290) and Saint Nicolò in Treviso (1303). The Gothic style arrived in Venice late, due to the cultural ties of the lagoon city with Byzantium, which were strengthened after the Fourth Crusade and the conquest of Constantinople in 1204. Around the middle of the 13th century, the domes of Saint Marco were enlarged as a response to the modern project of the basilica of Saint Antonio in Padua. In the enormous cross-vaulted mendicant basilicas of Saint Maria Gloriosa dei Frari (starting from 1330) and of Saints John and Paul (starting from 1333) the architectural form of Saint Nicolò in Treviso was emulated: the main choir had a height equal to those of the naves and transept, increasing the luminosity of the eastern sector (Dellwing, 2010, pp. 50-110).

In conclusion, the builders of the Franciscan reconstruction of Saint Fermo demonstrated great skills, inserting themselves as protagonists in the cultural context of the Gothic Veneto: they were able to vary some architectural and decorative parts, which demonstrate an enrichment during construction between the first and second construction phases (the alternating use of windows with pointed arches and single or double lancet windows with polychrome arches; the north transept is decorated only with intertwined arches, while the south one is decorated with a pattern of circles and crosses and has soaring spires, like the main apse). Furthermore, the builders used diversified decorative models: the crossed arches are of Lombard origin, while the cusps and pinnacles are of transalpine origin. The Franciscans commissioned a hybrid architecture that masterfully blends the Veronese Romanesque tradition (crypt) with Gothic innovation (church) and, for this reason, has no punctual comparison with other mendicant buildings in Northern Italy.

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Figure 1: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. Plans of the crypt and the monastery (Survey: Geogrà, 2016-2018. Courtesy of: Parish of S. Fermo, Diocese of Verona).

Figure 2: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. The crypt (photo: Angelo Passuello, 2022).

Figure 3: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. Cross section (east side) and orthophoto of the eastern front (Survey: Geogrà, 2016-2018. Courtesy of: Parish of S. Fermo, Diocese of Verona).

Figure 4: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. The wooden ceiling with an upturned ship's bottom (photo: Angelo Passuello, 2018).

Figure 5: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. Longitudinal section (north side) and orthophoto of the northern side (Survey: Geogrà, 2016-2018. Courtesy of: Parish of S. Fermo, Diocese of Verona).

Figure 6: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. Cross section (west side) and orthophoto of the façade (Survey: Geogrà, 2016-2018. Courtesy of: Parish of S. Fermo, Diocese of Verona).

Figure 7: Verona, Basilica of S. Fermo. The interior of the church (photo: Angelo Passuello, 2022).